

A Note on the Main Constituents of the dried Rind of the Fruit of *Garcinia Gambogia*.

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Sudborough and Vridhachalam have investigated the tartaric acid content of tamarind (*J. Indian Inst. Sci.*, 1920, 3, 61) and Bathum and Nigam have also investigated tamarind as a source of alcohol and tartaric acid (*Bull. Agr. Res. Inst. Pusa*, 1924, No. 153). No work appears to have been done on *Garcinia Gambogia*, the dried rind of the fruit of which finds a wide use in Cochin, Travancore and South Malabar, as a condiment, very much as tamarind and kokum (*G. Indica*) are used in other parts of the country. "Kadumpuli," as the dried rind of the fruit of *G. Gambogia* is known in Malayalam, is now found to contain about 10% of tartaric acid.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The rind (10 g.) was refluxed with 200 c.c. of water. The filtered extract, on neutralisation with ammonia gave a flocculent precipitate containing iron, calcium, magnesium, phosphate and tartrate. The filtrate showed the presence of sodium, potassium, citrate, tartrate, and reducing sugar. The inorganic constituents were confirmed by the analysis of the ash obtained by incinerating the dried rind.

Free Acids.—The rind (10 g.) was four times extracted with definite quantities of boiling water, till free from acids. The accumulated extracts, made up to a known volume, were titrated against standard sodium hydroxide solution, using phenolphthalein as indicator. 100 G. of the rind required 11.48 and 11.45 g. of sodium hydroxide respectively in two determinations.

Extracts.

Name of the constituents found.	Aqueous.	Acid.	Alkaline.	Method of determination
(a) Tartaric acid as potassium hydrogen tartrate.	10 p. c.	(1) 12.5 p. c. (2) 9.3 p. c.	--	Goldenberg's method (Sudborough and Vridhachalam, <i>loc. cit.</i> p. 65, 50 g. of material employed each time.
(b) As Ba-salt = potassium hydrogen tartrate = tartaric acid	4.11 g. 13.6 p. c. 10.6 p. c.	4.09 g. 13.6 p. c. 10.6 p. c.	4.16 g. 13.7 p. c. 10.7 p. c.	8 G. of material employed each time. The Ba-salt was prepared by a method which was analogous to that of Sudborough and Vridhachalam for Ca-salt (<i>loc. cit.</i> p. 66).
Phosphoric acid as calcium triphosphate	1.52 p. c.	1.52 p. c.	1.54 p. c.	Determined by means of uranium nitrate.
Reducing sugars as glucose.	7.4 p. c.	(1) 15.1 p. c. (2) 15.2 p. c.	14.8 p. c.	By means of standard Fehling's solution. The two acid extracts contained 10 and 15 c.c. of conc. HCl respectively.

N.B.—Polarimetric determinations were not helpful as concentrated extracts were not clear, and clear solutions were too dilute.